

Forced Migration and Adjustment challenges: A Study of Rohingya from Myanmar staying in Jammu & Kashmir

Paper Id : 18569 Submission Date : 13/02/2024 Acceptance Date : 19/02/2024 Publication Date : 25/02/2024

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10700569

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Abstract

For a long time, the Rohingya minority in Myanmar has been subjected to the worst forms of persecution. Presently, about 40,000 Rohingya refugees reside in India; they have also sought asylum in several other countries, including as Bangladesh, Malaysia, and Thailand. Around 5,600 of them came to Jammu and Kashmir for shelter. Forcible migrants and refugees find it exceedingly challenging to settle in a new location. Moving to a new location can be tough for anybody, but refugees have additional challenges that must be overcome, such as learning the language, establishing a support system, finding work, finding accommodation, adjusting to a new culture, etc. The difficulties that the Rohingya have in adjusting to Jammu City, where they are travelling, have been examined in this paper.

Keywords Accommodation, Refugees, Persecution, Adjustment.

Introduction

Rohingya are muslims from Arakan state of Myanmar. According to Yegar, 'the Arakanese Muslims call themselves Rohingya or Roewengyah, which means the 'dear ones,' the compassionate ones or those who believe in the mutilation of words Rwa-haung-ga-kar, 'tiger' from the ancient village which means brave and was a name given to Muslim soldiers who settled in Buthidaung' (Bhonsale, 2015).

It is critical to acknowledge that for Rohingya, relocating is a difficult process that takes time and effort. Moving to a new location can be tough for anybody, but refugees have additional challenges that must be overcome, such as learning the language, establishing a support system, finding work, finding accommodation, adjusting to a new culture, etc. Individuals need to adapt to changes in their own personalities as well as those brought on by shifts in their socioeconomic surroundings (Singh, Edbor, & Dingra, 2017). This study has analysed the process of home adjustment of Rohingya at their place of destination i.e. Jammu city which is the Union Territory of India.

Aim of study

1. To understand Housing adjustment.
2. To understand challenges related to it.

Review of Literature

Forced migration

There are various reasons for forced migration of any community. Political or religious persecutions, as well as other coercive factors like partition, are the root causes of forced migration (Castles, 2003). Migration that results from some sort of compulsion or threat to wellbeing or survival emerging in conditions ranging from violent conflict to severe economic hardship (Bartram, Poros, & Monforte, 2014). As a result, many were forced to flee their home countries in search of safety abroad, leaving them without a state and turning them into refugees (Uddin, 2020).

Adjustment

Adjusting to a new place can be challenging for anyone, but refugees face a unique set of difficulties like language learning, building a support network, employment, housing, cultural adjustment etc.

Methodology

The nature of this paper is descriptive. Data has been collected using Snowball sampling and Purposive sampling approaches. For this investigation, both primary and secondary data were utilised. Since numerous Rohingya have been residing in Jammu city for the past ten or twelve years, these individuals served as the respondents for this research. In this work, secondary data sources such as books, journal articles, papers, government manuals, and magazines pertaining to the topic of study have also been consulted. Through the use of a semi-structured interview schedule, primary data was obtained. SPSS software has also been used for the analysis of results and data. In this study, respondents are selected by using purposive sampling. Due to the fact that it denotes the deliberate selection of sample units that meet specific predetermined criteria, purposely, only those respondents have been selected who have been staying there for more than five years. Accordingly, a sample of 70 respondents who are the head of the family was chosen from Jammu city and interviewed. Moreover, the translator's help has also been sought as and when required to interview the respondents who did not know the local language.

Analysis

In order to collect primary data for this study, the researcher employed a semi-structured interview schedule in the field while documenting respondents' answers. In interviews with individuals who did not speak Hindi or English as their first language, translators have also been engaged. Using programmes like SPSS and Microsoft Office Word/Excel, the collected data were coded and tabulated prior to analysis.

Result and Discussion

Forced Migration

The military approach that the government of Myanmar has been seeking for this problem has shown to be extremely ineffective over time. Actually, over time, it has made things worse. The offensives become extremely deadly at the start of this year, killing thousands of civilians and driving an equal number of refugees to China and Thailand (Chaturvedi, 2012). When an estimated 3,000–4,000 Rohingya were discovered protesting in May 2012 and demanding legal protection and aid, as well as the UNHCR documentation that would have given them refugee cards, made this community visible. The Rohingya have been arriving in India gradually since the late 1970s. For a few years, they were unknown (Chaudhury & Samaddar, 2015).

Housing adjustment and challenges related to it

This study analysed the process of home adjustment of Rohingya at their place of destination i.e. Jammu city which is the Union Territory of India. Put simply, it refers to the manner in which they are coping with and fulfilling their requirements from the social and physical surroundings of the host community, namely Jammu City, as well as the difficulties they encounter in doing so. Forced migrants first sought for temporary housing after being uprooted in camps, emergency shelters, or on a leasing basis with host families. These accommodations are often basic and provide limited privacy and comfort. As forced migrants seek more permanent solutions, they may move into transitional housing facilities. They may also face various challenges at their place of destination including housing adjustment. Information has been collected from the respondents about the type of house they are living in. Table, type of house or accommodation of Respondents is given as under:

Type of Accommodation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Kaccha House (mud and wooden)	52	74.2

Pacca House (concrete)	04	5.8
Semi built	14	20
Total	70	100

After the analysis of data it was revealed that 74.2 percent of the respondents were living in the katch house or house made up of mud, wooden etc. and only a few were living in pacca house that was 5.8 percent and rest 20 percent were in semi built houses. Respondents also told that they have been facing various challenges and problems related to their houses at their place of destination. Housing adjustment for forced migrants can be a complex and challenging process, often involving various stages and considerations. For example, affordability, discrimination, legal barriers, language and cultural differences etc affordability migrants, especially those with limited financial resources, may struggle to afford housing in their destination country. High rental costs and housing prices relative to income levels can pose significant barriers to accessing suitable accommodation. Discrimination refers to migrants face discrimination from landlords or property owners based on factors such as ethnicity, nationality, or immigration status. Discriminatory practices can limit housing options and perpetuate social exclusion and marginalization. Legal Barriers: Legal restrictions, such as residency requirements or documentation criteria, can impede migrants' access to housing. In some cases, migrants may lack the necessary documentation to rent or purchase property legally, leaving them vulnerable to exploitation and housing insecurity. Language and cultural differences migrants who are unfamiliar with the local language or cultural norms may encounter challenges in communicating with landlords, understanding rental agreements, or navigating housing regulations. Language barriers can hinder effective communication and exacerbate issues related to housing access and integration.

Conclusion

This study discussed the challenges related to housing arrangements for Rohingya. It highlights various obstacles faced by them, including housing affordability issues, discrimination, legal barriers, language and cultural differences, overcrowding, lack of social support networks, and integration challenges. These challenges contribute to housing insecurity and hinder their ability to access safe and suitable accommodation. Addressing these issues requires comprehensive policies and initiatives that prioritize migrant rights, promote inclusive housing practices, and support integration and social inclusion. Collaboration between governments, civil society organizations, and local communities is crucial to address these challenges effectively and ensure that forced migrants have access to dignified housing options.

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